

October 2025

SAPEA Expert Workshop Report

Artificial Intelligence in Emergency and Crisis Management

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- SAPEA (2025). *Artificial intelligence in emergency and crisis management: Expert workshop report*. Munich: SAPEA.
- 10.5281/zenodo.17659552
- Downloadable from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17659552>

Version history

Version	Date	Summary of changes
1.0	11 December 2025	Publication

Scientific Advice Mechanism

to the European Commission

Artificial Intelligence in Emergency and Crisis Management

SAPEA Expert Workshop Report

6 October 2025

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Summary

This report summarises the discussions of an online workshop, held on 6th October 2025, to provide feedback on the draft SAPEA Rapid Evidence Review Report, The Role and Use of AI for Emergency and Crisis Management.

The Rapid Evidence Review Report addresses the main questions posed by DG ECHO: Based on the evidence, what are the characteristics, opportunities and risks associated with the use of artificial intelligence in crisis preparedness and response? According to the literature, how can these risks be mitigated?

Invited experts were asked to provide written feedback on the draft Report, addressing both its strengths and how it could be strengthened further.

Existing strengths of the Report identified by the experts included: its comprehensiveness, balance and interdisciplinarity; clarity and accessibility; operational relevance.

Areas to be strengthened identified by the experts included:

- Clearer structure and guidance (for example, by using graphics and giving reference points for policymakers)
- Prioritising potential areas of application (alongside indicators of AI maturity and readiness)
- Providing greater consistency in the formatting of case studies (as well as a critical evaluation of AI's real-world performance)
- Flagging risks around data availability (which might be addressed by a European dataspace)
- More testing of AI reliability (and the advantages of ensemble modelling)
- Further emphasis on a socio-technical perspective (and the need for hybrid intelligence)
- Updating the cited literature (alongside acknowledging gaps and uncertainties in the evidence base).

The experts provided further one-off comments in writing, some of which were raised at the workshop and all of which were subsequently addressed by the Working Group.

An invited speaker addressed the topic of AI and resilience in military and civilian applications. He emphasised the issue of layered resilience (the interconnectedness of military and civil resilience). His message was that resilience and crisis management are also about dealing with interconnecting networks of the cyber, physical and social. He urged that AI in decision-making go beyond simple dashboards, towards more complex analytics.

Introduction

This document summarises the main points from an online workshop held on 6th October 2025. The purpose of the workshop was to provide feedback on the draft of a Rapid Evidence Review Report on *The role and use of AI for emergency and crisis management*, prepared by the SAPEA Working Group.

Invited experts attended and gave their views in a personal capacity and not as representatives of their employer or any other organisation with which they are associated. Chatham House rules were observed, with no attribution to any individual.

This workshop was conducted entirely online. A list of attendees is given in Annex 2 to this report.

Context and scope

The Specifications of Work (unpublished) set out the formal request for advice from DG ECHO to the Scientific Advice Mechanism (SAM). The Rapid Evidence Review Report by SAPEA synthesises the evidence in response to the main questions posed in the Specification of Work:

Based on the evidence, what are the characteristics, opportunities and risks associated with the use of artificial intelligence in crisis preparedness and response? According to the literature, how can these risks be mitigated?

Report of the Expert Workshop

Introduction

The programme for the workshop is set out in Annex 1.
A summary of each session is given below.

Welcome

All participants were warmly welcomed. They included invited experts, members of the SAPEA Working Group, members of the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors and staff of the European Commission, the JRC and SAPEA (see Annex 2 for a list of attendees).

The Scientific Advice Mechanism and the need for this Rapid Evidence Review Report

The Scientific Advice Mechanism provides independent scientific evidence and policy recommendations to the European institutions, by request of the College of Commissioners.

The Rapid Evidence Review Report was requested by DG ECHO in the European Commission, to address the role and use of artificial intelligence for emergency and crisis management. A small SAPEA Working Group was formed to draft the Report. Invited experts were then asked to provide written feedback on the draft, addressing both existing strengths and how it could be strengthened further (the feedback form is published as Annex 3). The workshop ended with a presentation by an invited expert on *AI and resilience in military and civilian applications*.

Introduction to the SAPEA Rapid Evidence Review Report

Introduction by the Coordinator

In 2022, DG ECHO requested science advice on strategic crisis management, leading to the publication of a comprehensive Evidence Review Report and a Scientific Opinion¹; both were well received. In 2025, DG ECHO made a follow-up request, to examine the use of AI in crisis management. This would be a more concise, faster and targeted Rapid Evidence Review Report. The Report provides an evidence synthesis, with options for policy. It has a focus on preparedness and response, which are relevant for the EU's Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC). SAPEA assembled a core Working Group of seven international experts, who drafted the Report. SAPEA then invited a wider group of experts to provide feedback, with the aim of further strengthening the evidence base. The final Rapid Evidence Review Report is published in December 2025.

1 Available at: <https://scientificadvice.eu/advice/strategic-crisis-management-in-the-eu/>

Introduction by DG ECHO

DG ECHO expects to use the Rapid Evidence Review Report to inform discussions on the role and the use of AI, both for day-to-day as well as anticipated operations. The analytical team in the Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) provides analysis for civil protection operations - improving situational awareness, as well as offering mapping and operational recommendations. Scientific input is both in-house, from experts in DG ECHO working with the Joint Research Centre (JRC) and services like the Copernicus Emergency Management Service, and also from outside, involving scientific partnerships across Europe to provide advice on ongoing and imminent emergencies, including natural, radiological, nuclear and chemical hazards. The team seeks ways to enhance its capacities and is exploring AI with the JRC and DG Connect. It saw a need to improve the following: insight into the opportunities and challenges of AI; understanding how AI is applied to tasks in disaster and emergency management; and what is known about the reliability and maturity of AI applications. These could include, for example, the monitoring and forecasting of hazards, situational awareness, damage assessment and decision-making. The hope is that the Rapid Evidence Review Report will serve not only the ERCC and DG ECHO, but also the wider civil protection community. It will inform a workshop on resilience to natural hazards through AI solutions, held in conjunction with a third meeting of the UN-led *Global Initiative on Resilience to Natural Hazards through AI Solutions*² on 12th December.

Introduction by the SAPEA Working Group Chair

The SAPEA Rapid Evidence Review Report adopts a faster approach than a normal SAPEA Evidence Review Report. As AI is developing incredibly quickly, the Working Group has avoided looking at specific tools, as these would quickly become outdated. Rather, the Report seeks to sketch out the state-of-the-art, the different approaches to AI, the specifics of AI for crisis and emergency management, and how AI can be applied in the field, as illustrated by case studies.

Strengths of the Report

The question posed to the invited experts was:

Taking into account the initial request from DG ECHO (the Specifications of Work), what do you see as the main strengths of the draft Rapid Evidence Review Report?

SAPEA analysed and presented a summary of the responses, grouped into thematic clusters. The presentation was followed by general discussion. A number of one-off comments were also submitted in writing, and these were either discussed during the workshop or considered separately; a summary is included as Annex 4.

2 <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/extcoop/ai4resilience/Pages/default.aspx>

Report of the Expert Workshop

Presentation by SAPEA

Most of the feedback is very complimentary about the Report. The general view is that it addresses the Specification of Work and identifies the appropriate issues. It is comprehensive, balanced and interdisciplinary in approach. The evidence base is strong and broad. The report is clear and accessible and would be useful to policymakers and practitioners. It is operationally relevant, with policy options that would be actionable.

Discussion

The general discussion picked up the following points:

- One of the policy options focuses on AI literacy, and this is indeed a gap within Member States. The Report could feed into a planned e-learning programme, for example. The policy options are useful, because they are specific and concrete; they cite advantages and disadvantages, and are actionable.
- It is beneficial that one of the case studies is on digital risks. The Report also outlines situations in which it is advisable *not* to use AI, and when it is helpful to query responses from AI.

Strengthening the report

The question posed to the invited experts was:

Taking into account the initial request from DG ECHO (see the Specifications of Work), how do you think the draft Rapid Evidence Review Report can be strengthened?

SAPEA analysed and presented the responses, grouped into thematic clusters. The presentation of these was then followed by general discussion.

Presentation by SAPEA

1. Structure and signposting of the Report

The first cluster of comments is around the Report's structure and guidance for readers, particularly policymakers and non-experts. The Report needs a clearer structure, with an overarching framework at the beginning. There could be greater coherence between the different sections of the Report, so that it guides the reader through it in a more logical way. Another cluster of comments is about offering more points of reference for policymakers, bringing together information through tables and matrices, sample templates and protocols. A further recommendation is to make greater use of visuals and graphics.

2. Applications and case studies

A second cluster is around applications and case studies. It would be helpful to give an indication of priorities, by identifying 'low-hanging fruits' as well as areas where AI should not be used. This could be

accompanied by indicators of AI maturity and readiness, perhaps estimating the time to deployment. A further point is on providing more concrete, real-world examples. The section on case studies needs a more consistent structure and format. The case studies should be clearer about what they are trying to demonstrate, explaining how AI has contributed, and whether it has been effective or not. There are also ideas for additional case studies.

3. Data and modelling

A third cluster is around data and modelling. Consideration could be given to providing indicators of the representativeness of datasets, along with data provenance. There are risks around dependency on foreign data and exposure to restricted data flows. It is suggested that a European data space could be a policy option. The comment is made that AI itself can be a means of improving data quality. Mention of the quality and representativeness of the algorithmic models used to process data is missing in the Report. It is felt there should be greater emphasis on testing the reliability of AI in models, and that greater use of ensemble models could be helpful. Further, it is emphasised that decision-making tools should be tested independently using, for example, a dual or hybrid model.

4. Framings and the evidence base

The fourth cluster is on framings and the evidence base. The report's socio-technical perspective is seen as a plus, but there are suggestions on how to strengthen this further. For example, the user interface could be an element in building trust. AI is also seen as a means of assisting in local situations, overcoming national and cultural differences. Lastly, there is an emphasis placed on hybrid intelligence, with cooperation between AI and people, rather than AI replacing human expertise. On the evidence base, experts suggest updating the literature, together with identifying gaps and uncertainties in knowledge and research. Lastly, the report should critically evaluate AI's real-world effectiveness.

5. One-off comments

There are a number of one-off comments across a range of subjects, for example:

- There should be emphasis on prevention and long-term recovery, not just preparedness and response.
- The relationships between hazards should be highlighted.
- Cost-benefit analysis is raised as a means to prioritise intervention and resource allocation during crises. There is a need for more investment in AI for crisis management.
- It would be helpful to summarise the risks of AI, which are scattered throughout the Report, and to collate these by means of a risk matrix.
- Another point is on AI safety and cybersecurity, and the need for AI to be able to self-validate inputs.
- Mention of environmental impact is seen as positive, but it would be good to quantify the impact and to monitor energy use during the use of AI.
- In terms of legal frameworks, the point is made that these need to be considered early on, from the project design phase onwards.

Report of the Expert Workshop

- There should be more emphasis on end-user training.
- Lastly, the use of effective public communications could be a means of building trust.

Discussion

Points made during the discussion have been loosely clustered by topic:

Structure of the report

- It could be helpful to link the HABA-MABA³ framework mentioned in the Report to broader discussions around 'human-in-the-loop' etc and whether this could be shown in a visual.
- There is some repetition in the report that should be addressed.

Applications and case studies

- Some examples of where AI has been successful could be useful; it could draw on recent work published by Google, for example.
- At the same time, it is risky to rely too much on AI, given that the technology may fail, or essential infrastructure such as electricity may go down.
- A further point is that research on AI could benefit from the experience of experts on the field, rather than relying so much on computer scientists.
- Further indication of where not to use AI could be very helpful to policymakers.
- Combining the availability of tools with actual case studies is rare. There are plenty of tools, but communities or organisations may not have the capacity or resources to implement them. The capacity to use them needs to be enhanced; partnering with organisations to develop use cases or projects would be helpful.

Data and modelling

- Challenges with models and decision-making are not limited to AI models. Models needed to be tested with independent data, regardless of whether they are AI-assisted. Ensemble modelling, using physical and AI models, could be a significant advantage. Actual decision-making processes involve political, moral and other considerations.
- There is little community consensus on what an out-of-sample dataset could be for testing the reliability of weather models using AI. A community-defined train-test split for AI models may provide some community consensus, given that current benchmarking and tests are haphazard.
- Creating a European data space could simplify data integration and facilitate the application of AI models in different environments. Standardised interfaces could ensure that solutions are transferrable between countries and organisations. Currently, first responders are using different systems; they face challenges like vendor lock-ins and issues of interoperability. Open standards are valuable for data gathering, along with ensuring compliance and transparency on what data was used for decision-making. It is important to reference everything from social, digital and physical

3 Humans-are-better-at/machines-are-better-at

perspectives. It is important to work with people who use these systems daily and not just prepare for a one-off situation.

- A single AI model cannot deal with multiple types and levels of uncertainty. As mentioned, a multi-model ensemble can be advantageous. There is a requirement for precise definitions of uncertainty and how it is quantified. A flagging mechanism can bring a human into the loop as a check, for example, under conditions of significant uncertainty.
- Dependency mapping could show where Europe is critically dependent on access to others' data.

Framings and evidence

- It would be very helpful to set out the methodology of the Report more clearly. The Report provides extensive evidence about the potential of AI but does not give a clear indication of operational effectiveness on the ground, and what evaluation of performance has been done. If this evidence does not exist or is uncertain, it should be stated upfront in the Report.

Other comments

- It is important to highlight the limitations of AI approaches in unprecedented situations, in particular extreme weather events; this could include an additional case study.
- Another concern is that AI might be introduced as a way to reduce costs and replace human expertise.
- Disaster risk management includes prevention and reducing risk; it is not clear whether this is within the scope of the Report (DG ECHO confirmed that the ERCC focuses more on preparedness and response, but some coverage of prevention might be helpful).
- A section that reflects on barriers to adoption could be helpful. An example here would be the difficulty to integrate new AI products into national emergency management plans. Similarly, the option for developing a standard evaluation framework (Option 3 in the Report) could be very challenging.
- The newly emerging topic of agentic AI deserves greater coverage.
- Cybersecurity is an important issue.
- Levels of confidence in the technology are also important, linked to close cooperation with end users.
- Explanatory accountability and justification should be highlighted in the Report. This is challenging, as a crisis situation is often highly uncertain and information is limited. An emergency can be classed as a 'stated exception', under which law can be suspended. In a smaller crisis, constitutional frameworks still apply, so it is necessary to justify intrusions into privacy and other rights. There are national security and military exceptions in the AI Act, but legal frameworks lag behind what is a very fast-moving domain.

AI and resilience in military and civilian applications

Crisis management is an area where both civil and military actors can be involved. Dr Igor Linkov, Adjunct Professor at Carnegie Mellon University and Senior Scientific and Technical Manager with the US Army Engineer Research and Development Center, was invited to outline the sorts of collaboration that already exist or could exist. His views do not represent those of the US Government.

Presentation by Dr Linkov

Dual-use research is an area where both science and governance are important. On the governance side, the US Army Corps of Engineers is an example of a federal agency that has both civilian and military missions. On the civilian side, it is responsible for complex installations that it manages in constructions like bridges, energy systems and navigation. On the military side, it is responsible for military construction, the management of military installations and contingency operations.

The science of disruptions and emergency needs to be developed to address cascading failures, in response to compounding threats in both civilian and military systems. AI can be used in risk management, business continuity, and resilience analytics, all of which are essential in both military and civilian settings. There is a pacing problem, in that the technology evolves fast, whereas there is a lag in data about the use of this technology. The ability of regulatory communities to collect evidence, make decisions and develop protocols is even further behind. Agentic AI dominates the field currently, but is little mentioned in the Report; the evidence may not be published yet. By focusing on whether AI can supplement people in crisis management, as the Report does, the published evidence on this already exists. The strategy should be to transition from explainable AI to interpretable AI and resilient AI, increasing connectivity to decision-makers in the process⁴. It includes moving from simple visualisation tools used in explainable AI, to decision and resilience analytics for a real-world crisis situation.

A second point is about interconnectedness. Recently, NATO, in the Warsaw Declaration, defined layered resilience, meaning civil and military interconnectedness⁵.

A further point concerns the nature of emergencies, and the increase in compounding events and cascading failures⁶. The Report could map onto the typology of crisis rather than only focusing on preparing and responding. For example, Gartner views crisis management as resilience management. Much of Dr Linkov's research focuses on resilience by design and intervention, i.e. how to design for recovery before a crisis happens, and how to intervene to shorten recovery time and improve adaptation. The key is on measuring resilience; the approach is to fuse risk management that utilises threat vulnerability consequences, with resilience that focuses on recovery and adaptation. This is termed a resilience matrix. For AI in decision-making, it is important to transition from simple

4 Linkov, I., Galaitsi, S., Trump, B. D., Keisler, J. M., & Kott, A. (2020). Cybertrust: From explainable to actionable and interpretable artificial intelligence. *Computer*, 53(9), 91-96.

5 Keenan, J. M., Trump, B., Kytömaa, E., Adlakha-Hutcheon, G., & Linkov, I. (2024). The role of science in resilience planning for military-civilian domains in the U.S. and NATO. *Defence Studies*, 1–32.

6 Dulin, S., Smith, M., Ellinport, B., Trump, B., Keenan, J. M., & Linkov, I. (2025). Quantifying the compounding effects of natural hazard events: a case study on wildfires and floods in California. *npj Natural Hazards*, 2(1), 40.

dashboards that visualise information for the decision maker, to more complex analytics. AI can help in in descriptive, diagnostic, preventive, predictive and prescriptive analytics.

Dr Linkov cited examples from a couple of case studies to illustrate civilian and military uses of AI, and how to deal with compounding threats. One case was the environment, which is very important for the military, given that military installations are affected by natural disasters. This work is focused on what happens if flood and wildfire are collocated. He gave the example of Ukraine and contested logistics, where drones and satellite imagery are used to work out how the environment is recovering and how to minimise environmental damage, using AI tools and modelling. The same logic can be applied on the civilian side, giving the examples of wildfires and flood in North Carolina and California.

Another issue is network separation, such as interconnected energy and water networks⁷. Using a combination of AI and quantum computing, it is possible to optimise decision-making on how to separate networks. On the civilian side, it is feasible to divide wildfires, enabling us to deal with them in real time. Wildfire dynamics are such that they cannot be predicted, and it is vital to react immediately. Another application is in contested logistics and supply chains; a large DARPA project is looking at a resilient supply and demand network. This applies in the food chain and in manufacturing, for example. An instance is in Ukraine, where it is used to determine optimal spending and repair strategies. On the civilian side, the approach is used in New York to enhance understanding of transportation networks. In summary, resilience and crisis management are about dealing with interconnecting networks of the cyber, physical and social.

Discussion

Following Dr Linkov's presentation, the following points were made:

- Data sharing and interoperability between civil and military environments can be challenging. A parallel structure for data is likely to persist.
- Hybrid set-ups, especially for logistics, are incredibly important. However, intelligence sharing is hard; AI tools are likely to be tailored towards certain values that are inherent in either military or humanitarian discourses. Nonetheless, there is room for cooperation, joint technology and research.
- The Red Cross is working in countries with protracted crises, where early-warning systems are not functional. AI can help here, such as the Google Flood Hub in Somalia. Using models and tools that allow real-time computation, it is possible to provide vital information to decision-makers. A challenge on the operational side is that models are now often multi-hazard or multi-risk, but many funding mechanisms are still siloed in single hazard trigger models. It is important to change the structure of crisis management to focus on resilience, including recovery and adaptation. Preparedness can be done for response, but also for recovery and adaptation. Both the system and funding need to be balanced between response and recovery.

⁷ Linkov, I., & Kott, A. (Eds.). (2025). *Cyber resilience: Applied perspectives*. Springer Nature Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-90109-6>

Annexes

Annex 1: Workshop programme

Item	
Welcome Objectives of the meeting Introduction to the SAM and SAPEA	Céline Tschirhart
Background and introduction to the request	DG ECHO
Approach to the request and general overview of the draft Rapid Evidence Review Report	Tina Comes
Feedback on the draft Report – What do you see as the main strengths of the draft Rapid Evidence Review Report? Summary of feedback General discussion	Summary: Louise Edwards Facilitation: Tina Comes
<i>Break</i>	
Feedback on the draft Rapid Evidence Review Report – How do you think the draft Rapid Evidence Review Report can be strengthened? Summary of feedback Round-robin of comments General discussion	Summary: Louise Edwards Facilitation: Tina Comes
AI and resilience in civilian and military emergencies Discussion	Background: Jonathan Murphy Presentation: Igor Linkov Facilitation: Tina Comes
Next steps and wrap-up Any other business	Céline Tschirhart
<i>Close</i>	

Annex 2: List of workshop attendees

SAPEA core group of experts

- Tina Comes (Chair), German Aerospace Center & TU Delft
- Verónica Bolón-Canedo, Universidade da Coruña
- Joachim Denzler, Friedrich Schiller University Jena
- Nick Jennings, Loughborough University
- Thomas Kox, Weizenbaum Institute
- Christian Reuter, TU Darmstadt
- Andrej Zwitter, University of Groningen

Invited experts

- Burcu Balçık, Özyeğin University
- Maurice de Beer, Rotterdam-Rijnmond Fire Service
- Marc Berenguer Ferrer, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain
- Quentin Brot, The French National Fire Officers Academy (ENSOSP)
- Mario Drobics, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology
- Adina Florea, National University of Science and Technology POLITEHNICA Bucharest (UNSTPB)
- Oskar Josef Gstrein, University of Groningen
- Marc van den Homberg, University of Twente
- Kai Kornhuber, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA)
- Olya Kudina, TU Delft
- Qihua Liang, Loughborough University
- Igor Linkov, US Army Corps of Engineers and adjunct professor at Carnegie Mellon University
- Marta López-Saavedra, Natural Risks Assessment and Management Service (NRAMS), Institute of Environmental Diagnosis and Water Research (IDAEA-CSIC), Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Spain
- Warner Marzocchi, University of Naples Federico II
- Shruti Nath, University of Oxford
- Karen Yeung, University of Birmingham
- Barbara Zitová, Czech Academy of Sciences

European Commission representatives

- Jaime Abad Perez (ECHO)
- Spyros Afentoulidis (ECHO)
- Miguel Alvarez Rodriguez (CNECT)

Annexes

- Anna Berlin (ECHO-EXT)
- Olimpia Imperiali (ECHO)
- Juha-Pekka Japola (ECHO)
- Evgenia Karatari (EEAS)
- Auriane Denis Loupot (ECHO)
- Michele Ronco (DRMKC)
- Mark Smitham (CNECT)
- Andrea Toretì (JRC-ISPRA)

Members of the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors to the European Commission

- Adam Izdebski, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń
- Martin Kahanec, Central European University;
Central European Labour Studies Institute in Bratislava
- Dimitra Simeonidou, University of Bristol
- Rémy Slama, Inserm & ENS, Paris
- Mangala Srinivas, Wageningen University and Research

SAM Secretariat, European Commission

- Annabelle Ascher, SAM Secretariat Policy Officer
- Geoffroy Delamare, SAM Secretariat Policy Officer
- Karen Fabbri, Deputy Head of Unit Science for Policy, Advice & Ethics
- Francesco Manetti, SAM Secretariat Trainee
- Scira Menoni, expert support to the SAM Secretariat
- Jonathan Murphy, SAM Secretariat Policy Officer
- Ingrid Zegers, SAM Secretariat Team Lead

SAPEA staff

- Céline Tschirhart, SAPEA Scientific Policy Officer (ALLEA)
- Louise Edwards, SAPEA Scientific Policy Officer (Cardiff University, Academia Europaea)
- Anda Popovici, SAPEA Scientific Policy Officer (Euro-CASE)
- Justine Moynat, SAPEA Communications Manager
- Lionel Dutrieux, SAPEA Digital Communications Officer
- Mariana Rei, SAPEA Scientific Policy Officer (Euro-CASE)
- Rudi Hielscher, SAPEA Manager

Annex 3: Feedback form

European Commission's Scientific Advice Mechanism

Scientific advice on the topic

The role and use of artificial intelligence for emergency and crisis management

Feedback form

Taking into account the initial request from DG ECHO (see the Specifications of Work), what do you see as the main strengths of the draft Rapid Evidence Review Report?

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Taking into account the initial request from DG ECHO (see the Specifications of Work), how do you think the draft Rapid Evidence Review Report can be strengthened?

Please share here published evidence that could help strengthen the Report.

Annex 4. Summary of feedback

The following is a non-exhaustive summary of comments received from the invited experts, prior to the workshop:

Strengths of the Report

- Addresses the Specification of Work, identifies appropriate issues
- Comprehensive overview, balanced, interdisciplinary
- Strong and broad evidence base
- Forward-looking
- Clear and accessible, useful for policymakers and practitioners
- Operationally relevant, with actionable policy options

Areas that could be strengthened further

Report structure and guidance for readers

- Provide a clearer structure that guides policymakers
- Include an overarching framework at the beginning and create more coherence between sections of the report
- Offer more points of reference for policymakers, for example, interconnecting frameworks, matrices and tables, templates, and protocols
- Improve reader accessibility, for example, through increased use of visuals, graphics, matrices, tables

Applications and case studies

- Prioritise AI applications, for example:
- Identify 'low-hanging fruits' where AI could be used
- Areas where AI should NOT be used
- Provide indicators of AI maturity, readiness, time to deployment
- Give more concrete, real-world examples, and design a more consistent structure and format
- Be clearer about what each case study is trying to demonstrate, and how AI contributes
- Offer more success stories that show where AI has been applied effectively in crisis management

Data and modelling

- Data
- Suggest indicators of representativeness and sources of data
- Address risks of foreign data dependency and restricted data flows
- Consider the option for a European data space

- Propose AI itself as a means to improve data quality
- Algorithms
- Address issues around the algorithmic models used to process data
- Models
- Put greater emphasis on testing the reliability of AI forecasting models
- Consider the use of ensemble models for enhanced forecasts
- Emphasise the importance of decision-making tools that are independent of models and remain constant throughout the crisis/emergency

Framings and evidence base

- Put even greater emphasis on the socio-technical perspective, for example:
- The user interface as an element in building trust
- AI as a means to assist in local situations, overcoming issues like national and cultural differences
- Hybrid intelligence
- Evidence base
- Check for new literature
- Identify gaps and uncertainties in knowledge and research
- Clarify the gap between the potential of AI and genuine real-world effectiveness

One-off comments

- Emphasise prevention and long-term recovery, not just preparedness and response
- Highlight relationships between hazards (not only individual hazards)
- Consider cost-benefit analysis of AI, as a way to prioritise intervention and resource allocation during crises
- Stress the need for more investment in AI for crisis management
- Draw together and highlight key risks and limitations of AI in crisis management; include a risk matrix
- Provide more text on AI safety, cybersecurity; the need for AI to be able to self-validate inputs
- Quantify environmental impact, monitor and report on energy use
- Underline the need for early consideration of EU legal frameworks (from the project design phase onwards)
- Highlight the need for more end-user training
- Promote the benefits of effective public communications to build trust

A number of editorial changes to the text were also suggested, including strengthening the executive summary. Experts also provided additional references and a list of projects.

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Within the Scientific Advice Mechanism, SAPEA is funded by the European Union (grant number 101198044).

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